

	Deliverable Title DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	Ref. D4.2	Issue A
	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary COMPOSITADOUR	Work Package WP4	Date 14/12/2020

Object: Project deliverable

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 886549. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

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MODIFICATIONS INDEX

Issue	Date	Reviews
A	14/12/2020	Creation

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1. Introduction

1.1. Generic introduction

The Data Management Plan describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and generated by the FRAMES project.

FRAMES DMP includes information on :

- The handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- Which methodology and standards will be applied
- Whether data will be shared/made open access and how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)

FRAMES partners are committed to ensure data generation is soundly managed, in line with the Horizon 2020 objectives to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. FRAMES partners have signed in to be part of the Open Research Data Pilot with the commitment to give open access to the data generated until it goes against confidentiality, commercial interests or Intellectual property.

FRAMES DMP is intended to be a living document to be updated throughout the project with generated results. To ensure accessibility of the data, FRAMES DMP applies through the whole duration of activities until the last update of data.

The following terms will be used within the document :

- Metadata : this is a short explanation, summary or key information of what the data is. Metadata facilitate search requests, discovery, reuse and spread of information to third parties.
- Data set : this is a collection of data, to be considered as a whole for relevance and concrete result.
- Embargo period : this the total duration of data capture and storage, expressed in years generally but pending on data type and value.

1.2. Contacts

1.2.1. COMPOSITADOUR

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1.3. Abbreviations

DMP : Data Management Plan

FAIR : Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable

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FRAMES : Fibre Reinforced thermoplastic Manufacturing for stiffened, complex, double curved Structures

ORDP : Open Research Data Pilot

PGA : Project General Assembly

DOI : Digital Object identifier

JU : Joint Undertaking

1.4. Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results/ communication activity related to the project must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2. Data Summary

FRAMES project will generate and collect several types of data outputs, related to the following topics:

- Xenon heating device and system modelling
- Fiber placement lay up physical modelling
- Thermoplastic profiles and stiffeners manufacturing process
- Co-consolidation of thermoplastic composites structures
- Tooling solutions

Each data set created during the project will be assessed and classified as open, embargo or restricted by the owner of the content of the data set.

Open : Decision to disseminate. FRAMES provide free of charge access to scientific information

Embargo : Decision to disseminate after an embargo period is over.

Restricted : Decision to exploit / protect

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Figure 1 : FRAMES data management overview

The Project General Assembly, representing all Frames partners, will assess the nature of the data, balanced the partner interests with the necessity to disseminate and decide whether the data will be protected or released to the public. Before final decision, the project coordinator representing the PGA will inform the Topic Leader in accordance with the Implementation Agreement.

Within this project, it is intended to generate and collect different types of data as detailed in the following table. Other types, formats and contents may be added to this table during the project duration.

Data type	Data format	Content
Reports	.pdf, .docx, .doc, .pptx, .ppt, .txt, odt	Technical achievements, tests and trials results, meeting minutes, project deliverables
Raw data from trials, part control or simulation outputs	.xlsx, .xls, .csv, .dat, .ods, .odp	Thermocouples recordings, 3D part or component control, process simulation extracts
Archives	.zip, .7z, .rar	All data types and format detailed in present table
CAD models data set	.CATPart, .CATProduct, .step, .stp, .stl, .iges, .igs, .3dxml	Parts, Demonstrator and Tooling CAD models
Simulation models data set	.stp, .CATProcess, .cgr, .CATMaterial, .xml, .html, .src, .dat	Optical/thermal simulation, fiber placement simulation
Images	.png, .jpg, .jpeg, .bmp, tiff	Internal meetings, events participation, parts and

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		demonstrator, manufacturing trials, part controls, testing
Videos	.avi, .wmv, .mpeg, .mkv	Internal meetings, events participation, parts and demonstrator, manufacturing trials, part controls, testing
Radiometric videos	.ravi	Measurements from thermal camera

Table 1 : Data types, format and contents to be generated and collected within FRAMES project

Data may have various origins:

- Partners' background reused within FRAMES
- FRAMES results
- Bibliography, external publications and open access documents reused

Size of data may vary significantly pending on data types. Reports are usually under 100Mo size, but Radiometric videos files may easily be over 10Go each.

3. FAIR Data

As stated into the Grant Agreement, and underlined by the participation into the ORDP initiative, FRAMES partners will proceed to disseminate as soon as possible the project results to the public, unless it goes against their own legitimate interests.

It is reminded that FRAMES partners must ensure free of charge access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results and must in particular:

- as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;
- Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - o on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - o (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
 - ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking”, “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

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It is also remind that in terms of research data, FRAMES partners must in particular :

- deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - o (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
 - o (ii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’;
- (b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation detailed into the Grant Agreement, in particular the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

FRAMES research data and results will be deposited in :

- An internal SharePoint platform, hosted and managed by the project coordinator ESTIA to which only project partners have access
- An open access repository, Zenodo, ensuring that data can be founded by anyone.

To facilitate sharing and access, a specific attention will be paid on Metadata and files name standardisation. Metadata will have a key role to make uploaded data findable, in particular by the general public, using web search engines.

The following types of metadata will be defined as a basis for all public data released:

- Data description : Information such as data nature, author, title, date of publication and others data that can be used by anyone to identify quickly the content of the data
- Common metadata : Following the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020” as well as the article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement, bibliographic metadata will use a standard format and will includes the following terms :
 - o Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking
 - o European Union (EU)
 - o Horizon 2020

Additional terms common to all data generated within FRAMES project will also be used :

- o Project acronym : FRAMES
- o Project name : Fibre Reinforced thermoplAstics Manufacturing for stiffEned, complex, double curved Structures.
- o Project Grant number : 886549
- Specific metadata : Task leader will have to define keywords that considered to be relevant for the data and can be probably use during a search query.

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Metadata will first be defined by the task leader using a project standard template. Then, the data set with its metadata will be sent to project coordinator and the classification of the data (open, embargo, restricted) will be discussed and decided within the Project General Assembly. Then, for public categorized data, dissemination and communication task leader will use the data and metadata to fulfil requested information of the open access repository and will ensure effectiveness of the data access to the general public.

The project standard template includes the following fields to be complete according to the previous rules and recommendations:

- Reference: generated by a combination of project name, work package, task and consecutive number
- Description: comprehensive and concise description of data collected/generated, that can be readable and understandable by anyone (60 characters max.)
- Authors: Name of the data author
- Beneficiary: Author company name
- Origin: Data source, to be chosen between the following options :
 - o Observational data
 - o Laboratory experimental data
 - o Computer simulation
 - o Review
 - o Bibliography
 - o Other, to be specified
- Nature: Data nature, to be selected between the following options (with associated abbreviations for file format standard)
 - o Project deliverable DEL
 - o Technical reports TRE
 - o Meeting minutes MMI
 - o Standards / Methodology STD
 - o Publications / Press release PUB
 - o Raw data from trials, part control or simulation outputs RAW
 - o Archives ARC
 - o CAD models data set CAD
 - o Simulation models data set SIM
 - o Images IMG
 - o Videos VID
 - o Radiometric videos RVID
- Issue or version: Data version

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- Sharing classification : Sharing options, to be selected between the following options :
 - o Open : Public release
 - o Embargo : Public release after an embargo period applied by the publisher.
 - o Restricted : Strictly private, only for project use.
- Embargo period ending, if relevant : End date of the embargo period, must be written with the DD/MM/YYYY format.
- Date of publication : Date of data release
- Potential interest groups : At least one group to be selected between the following options :
 - o General public
 - o Aircrafts OEM and Tier 1 suppliers
 - o Composites industry stakeholders
 - o Research and academic community
 - o Public entities
 - o Other, to be specified
- Bibliographic reference, if relevant: details on data source, for example : persistent identifier or standard format if no persistent identifier is available : “Name & Surname of the author; Name of the paper. NAME OF THE PUBLICATION. DD/MM/YYYY. ISSN XXXX-XXXX”.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

To make information openly accessible to internal and external users and according best practises of “open data”, free files formats such as .pdf, .odt, .ods, .odp, .csv, .png, .mkv, .7z will be prioritized when uploading information.

Standardization of the names of the files stored will also contribute to improve data accessibility. A list of all files reference will be stored within project SharePoint platform.

Figure 2 : FRAMES files name standardization

3.3. Increase data re use (through clarifying licences)

As mentioned previously, each data set will be assessed and categorized as open, embargo or restricted by the owner of the data set.

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Open status :

- Zenodo repository : Data will be deposited under public status during the next month after they are finished.
- Internal SharePoint platform : Data will be deposited during the next month after they are finished.

Embargo status :

- Zenodo repository : Data will be deposited under embargo status during the next month after the publication
- Internal SharePoint platform : Data will be deposited during the next month after they are finished.

Restricted status :

- Data will only be deposited on the internal SharePoint platform only

3.4. Data storage and preservation

Original documents and data will be stored in the database of the entities that have created them.

Digital copies for internal uses will be placed on the Sharepoint platform, managed by ESTIA IT services. Files uploaded will be available at any time, and transferred to equivalent platform or information system if need be.

Digital copies for dissemination will be stored within the Zenodo, and automatically assigned with a DOI. Data is stored in the CERN cloud infrastructure which provide a long term and reliable data management.

4. Allocation of ressources

ESTIA is coordinator of the project and is taking charge of the dissemination and communication work package as well.

5. Data security

Data shared between the partners are in secured space on SharePoint platform provided by the coordinator, during the project duration.

A specific attention will be paid on ensuring that the data identified as publishable breaks neither partner IPR rules, nor regulations and good practices related to personal data protection.

6. Ethical aspects

In this project, there is no ethical issues that should be taken into consideration.

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7. Conclusion

FRAMES data management plan provides an overview of the data that will be collect and generated within the project duration. This document provide a baseline for project partners for efficient data management, and is intended to be a living document to complete over the project timeframe.

The FRAMES consortium is committed to share project results, however, as competitive pressure on aerospace and composites industry is growing, it has to be carefully balanced between strategic proprietary know-how strengthening partner position and the opportunity to reach a wide audience stimulating research initiatives and emerging applications.